

THE WORK “MONUMENTS LEFT BY ANCIENT PEOPLES” IS A UNIQUE PEARL OF NOMANOLOGY

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Annotation: The article discusses onomastic units used in Abu Rayhan Beruni’s work “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples”, particularly historical anthroponyms, geortonyms, chrononyms, toponyms, and cosmonyms. It provides information on the cosmonym Azvapachkirik, the toponym Al-Fir, and the geortonym Navruz Mehrjon. Historical names are one of the means that contribute to the awareness of national identity, attention to traditions and customs, which are the spiritual sources of peoples.

Keywords: onomastic units, anthroponym, geortonym, chrononym, cosmonym, etymology, phoneme.

The onomastic units, by their nature, are highly stable and minimally changing elements of language that are typically left untranslated in other languages. Due to this characteristic, the onomastic units in “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples” serve as the most reliable and authoritative evidence for any historical or linguistic research. The system of proper nouns comprises a significant portion of the lexicon in the language of “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples”, with numerous historical anthroponyms, geortonyms, cosmonyms, toponyms and mythonyms employed throughout the text of the work.

In Azamat Primov’s research work “Linguistic Features of Uzbek Cosmonyms”, it is noted that Beruni not only discussed the nature and movement of astronomical bodies but also provided valuable information on the principles of their naming and etymology. A. Primov has expressed his views on the fact that the Arabic and Turkic cosmonyms mentioned in the scientist’s works continue to be actively used in our present-day language . In addition, in the work “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples” it is written that the astrologer in the Khorezm language is called axtar venik and that the Khorezmians knew the zodiac signs better than the Arabs.

In his work “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples” the scholar provides information on the constellation called Azvapachkirik used in the Khorezmian language: The Khorezmians knew the zodiac signs better than the Arabs. The fact that the names given to the constellations correspond to the names given by the [astronomers] responsible for describing them, do not correspond to the Arabic [language], and the Arabs describe them through images other than those given by the officials shows the correctness of our words. For instance, the Arabs

placed Jawdah among the constellations in place of the image of a twin boy. However, Jawza is the star of the Almighty. The people of Khorezm call this constellation Azvapachkirik. This means “twin” .

Kh.Salihodzhaeva writes that Beruni’s work “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples” is one of the historical sources of chrononymy and geortonymy of the Uzbek language, and in her research work “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples” she dwells on the holidays and festivals of Khorezm and Sogdians in the pre-Islamic period .

In the work “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples”, it is written that during the time of the Prophet, people called years not by numbers, but by such names as “Year of Peace”, “Year of Victory”, “Year of Friendship”. Kh. Solikhodjaeva discusses that the linguocultural characteristics of the geortonyms Navruz and Mehrjon, citing references from the scholar’s information on festivals presented in the work “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples”.

According to some, Navruz is the first of the six days Allah created creation. Just as the Sun and Moon are the two eyes of the sky, so Navruz and Mehrjon are the two eyes of time .

The scientific heritage of our great ancestor is being studied not only in Uzbekistan, but also today on a global scale. In particular, research and studies are also continuing within the framework of nomology. In his article “Abu Rayhan Beruni’s Information on the Cosmonyms of Iranian-Speaking Peoples”, written by A. Mirboboyev and Yu. Boboyev, he cites the Arabic, Persian, Khorezmian, and Rumian names of the planets mentioned in his work “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples” and writes that some Sogdian and Khorezmian cosmonyms have been preserved in the Tajik language .

In his article “Interpretation of the Historical Onomastics of Khorezm in Abu Rayhan Beruni’s Works”, Yu. Boboev discusses the names of kings from the Khorezmshah Afrighid dynasty mentioned in the work “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples”, as well as the historical Khorezmian fortress known as Fir Castle .

Al-Fir – the name of the ancient capital of Khorezm, located on the left bank of the Amu Darya. In Arabic written sources, it is also called Al-Mansura. According to Beruni, Al-Fir was a fortress built of clay and unbaked bricks on the outskirts of the city of Khorezm, consisting of three-story fortresses nestled within each other and not inferior in height.

Among the ancient information presented to us by “Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples” its historical names used in various languages hold a special

place. A comprehensive and in-depth analysis of our great ancestor's research work provides valuable information about the languages of the peoples who lived in the period and territories where this book was written, and the remnants of these languages preserved in modern languages and folk dialects. In this sense, "Monuments Left by Ancient Peoples" are an invaluable historical and linguistic heritage.

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